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The refractive index-composition curves of certain acid-ketone and acid-ester systems have been investigated. The following are the systems studied:—(a) acid-ketone system:—(i) trichloro-acetic acid-acetone; (ii) acetic acid-acetophenone; (iii) propionic acid-acetone; (iv) *n*-butyric acid-acetone; (b) acid-ester system:—(i) trichloroacetic acid-ethyl benzoate; (ii) acetic acid-ethyl benzoate; (iii) acetic acid-ethyl acetate.

It has been found that in the above cases, except system (a, ii) the refractive index-composition curves are distinctly concave to the concentration axis, thus suggesting the formation of intermediate complexes

The refractive index-composition curves of binary liquid mixtures have been studied by various investigators (Pushin and Matavulj, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **161**, 341; **162**, 415; Burnham and Madgin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 789; Ansov, *Ann. Inst. Physico-chim, Leningrad*, 1926, **3**, 379, 455; Rao and Narayanaswamy, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, **9A**, 35).

According to Pushin and Matavulj, in systems where compound formation takes place, the refractivity curve shows positive deviations from the mixture law. In another investigation, Kendall and Brakeley (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1826) have shown with viscosity measurements, extensive compound formation in certain acid-ketone, acid-ester systems. Similar studies have been undertaken in the present investigation, with a view to typifying some of the binary systems from the variations of refractive indices with the composition.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The starting materials were Merck's extra pure reagents. They were further purified by repeated distillation. The variations in refractive index with composition have been shown in the succeeding tables. Pulfrich refractometer was used and sodium light employed. The refractive index for trichloroacetic acid has been calculated from its value of molecular refractivity.

TABLE I

Trichloroacetic acid: ethyl benzoate (at 20°)

Mol. % of the acid.	Refractive Index.
0	1'5059
7	1'5044
22	1'5026
32'6	1'5006
46'9	1'4974
65	1'4926
73'6	1'4887
82'4	1'4833
100	1'4727

TABLE II

Acetic acid: ethyl benzoate (at 18°)

Mol. % of the acid.	Refractive Index.
0	1'5059
12'03	1'4917
24'5	1'4764
38'8	1'4558
47'9	1'4463
53'6	1'4377
71'5	1'4131
83	1'3982
100	1'3719

TABLE III

Acetic acid: ethyl acetate (at 18°)

Mol. % of the acid.	Refractive Index.
0	1'3702
6'4	1'3710
16'3	1'3723
17'7	1'3725
29'9	1'3730
39'2	1'3731
46'1	1'3732
53'2	1'3731
63'9	1'3731
77'1	1'3728
100	1'3719

TABLE IV		TABLE V		TABLE VI		TABLE VII	
Trichloroacetic acid : acetone (at 20°)		Propionic acid : acetone (at 19.5°)		<i>n</i> -Butyric acid : acetone (at 17.5°)		Acetic acid : acetophenone (at 22°)	
Mol. % of acid.	Refractive Index.	Mol. % of acid.	Refractive Index.	Mol. % of acid.	Refractive Index.	Mol. % of acid.	Refractive Index.
0	1.3588	0	1.3588	0	1.3588	0	1.5342
10	1.3822	23	1.3678	20	1.3700	5.3	1.5279
15	1.3922	33	1.3710	29.9	1.3754	12.06	1.5170
18	1.3973	42.5	1.3740	43.9	1.3822	20.6	1.4994
30	1.4158	49.9	1.3759	51	1.3842	34.1	1.4801
37	1.4243	66	1.3802	70.2	1.3908	43.7	1.4634
52	1.4410	74.5	1.3820	80	1.3926	51.5	1.4513
69	1.4563	79.9	1.3831	91	1.3955	58.7	1.4393
80	1.4634	92	1.3850	100	1.3979	68.8	1.4240
100	1.4727	100	1.3865			81	1.4042
						100	1.3719

Fig. 1 shows the graphs obtained by plotting the refractive indices against the concentrations of one of the components of the binary mixtures. The inset in Fig. 1 shows the curve for the system ethyl acetate : acetic acid. In calculating the molar percentages, acetic acid

Curve I—Propionic acid—acetone
 Curve II—*n*-butyric—acetone
 Curve III—CCl₃COOH—acetone
 Curve IV—CCl₃COOH—ethyl benzoate
 Curve V—acetic acid—acetophenone
 Curve VI—acetic acid—ethyl benzoate
 Curve VII—acetic acid—ethyl acetate

has been taken to be dimeric since this is an associated liquid. In the cases studied it has been found that all the curves except curve V are markedly concave to the concentration axis. This points out that these systems do not obey the mixture law. These deviations from the mixture law leads to the inference that in these cases there is most probably formation of intermediate complexes. Such inferences were also drawn from a study of similar curves by Ansov (*loc. cit.*) who holds that curves concave to the concentration axis indicate reciprocal chemical action.

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